

THERMODYNAMICS OF SOLUTIONS OF MIXED ELECTROLYTES

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The thermodynamical treatment, developed by Srivastava and Rastogi (*Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci., India*, 1953, 19, 613), has been extended to multi-component ionic solutions.

While the thermodynamics of solutions of single electrolytes has been extensively treated (Guggenheim, "Thermodynamics", 1952; Harned and Owen, "The Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solution", 1943), the development of a thermodynamic theory for solutions of several electrolytes seems not to have received sufficient attention. In this paper an attempt has been made to extend the treatment developed by Srivastava and Rastogi (*Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*; 1953, 19, 613) to multi-component ionic solutions.

Condensed Phase in Equilibrium with Non-ideal Vapour

We will discuss the conditions of equilibrium in a system containing electrolytes 1, 2, i k (all binary) having no common ion dissolved in a solvent. We will denote the degrees of dissociation of these electrolytes by $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_i, \dots, \alpha_k$. If $n_1, n_2, n_3, \dots, n_i, \dots, n_k$ moles of the electrolyte are dissolved in n_s moles of the solvent, the number of moles of the different species of ions formed can be found out as follows:— n_i moles of the electrolyte i , when dissolved, will give $\alpha_i Z_{ia} n_i$ moles of anion, $\alpha_i Z_{ic} n_i$ moles of cation and $(1 - \alpha_i) n_i$ moles of the undissociated electrolyte, where Z_{ia} and Z_{ic} are the number of anions and cations respectively formed from one mole of the electrolyte, if we assume the dissociation to be complete. We will thus have $\sum_i \alpha_i Z_{ia} n_i$ moles of anions, $\sum_i \alpha_i Z_{ic} n_i$ moles of cations, and $\sum_i (1 - \alpha_i) n_i$ moles of undissociated electrolytes. The condition of electroneutrality is automatically satisfied from our basic assumption of the mechanism of dissociation and, hence, will not form a further restrictive condition. The mole fraction of the anion i will be given by

$$N_{ia} = \frac{\alpha_i Z_{ia} n_i}{\sum_{i=1}^k (\alpha_i Z_{ia} n_i + \alpha_i Z_{ic} n_i + 1 - \alpha_i n_i) + n_s} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

The mole fraction of the cation i will be given by

$$N_{ic} = \frac{\alpha_i Z_{ic} n_i}{\sum_{i=1}^k (\alpha_i Z_{ia} n_i + \alpha_i Z_{ic} n_i + 1 - \alpha_i n_i) + n_s} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

and the mole fraction of the undissociated electrolyte i will be given by

$$N_{iu} = \frac{(1 - \alpha_i)n_i}{\sum_{i=1}^k (\alpha_i Z_{ia} n_i + \alpha_i Z_{iu} n_i + \overline{1 - \alpha_i} n_i) + n_s} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Thus, we will have $3k + 1$ species in the solution including the solvent which will have mole fractions denoted by $N_{1a}, N_{1c}, N_{1u}; N_{2a}, N_{2c}, N_{2u}; \dots \dots; N_{ka}, N_{ic}, N_{iu}; \dots \dots; N_{ka}, N_{kc}, N_{ku}; N_s$. Out of these, however, not all will be independent, for we have the following relation between the mole fractions of the species formed from the same source i

$$\dots \quad \dots \quad \frac{N_{ia}S}{\alpha_i Z_{ia}} = \frac{N_{ic}S}{\alpha_i Z_{ic}} = \frac{N_{iu}S}{(1 - \alpha_i)} = n_i, \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

where S represents the denominator in equations (1), (2) and (3).

Further, we have the relationship

$$\sum_i (N_{ia} + N_{ic} + N_{iu}) + N_s = 1 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

so that, in all, the mole fractions of only k species will be independent.

In the foregoing, we have assumed that the degrees of dissociation of the electrolytes $\alpha_1, \alpha_2 \dots \alpha_i \dots \alpha_k$ do not vary with the concentration and temperature within a small range. This may be assumed to be approximately true of small changes in concentration, but the applicability of the equations derived below will be limited because of this restriction.

The general equation for liquid-vapour equilibrium can hence be represented as (Srivastava and Kastogi, *loc. cit.*):

$$\begin{aligned} & - \left\{ \frac{N_s L_s}{T} dT + \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{N_{ic} L_{ic}}{T} dT + \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{N_{ia} L_{ia}}{T} dT + \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{N_{iu} L_{iu}}{T} dT \right\} \\ & + N_s \bar{V}_s dP + \sum_{i=1}^k N_{ic} \bar{V}_{ic}' dP + \sum_{i=1}^k N_{ia} \bar{V}_{ia}' dP + \sum_{i=1}^k N_{iu} \bar{V}_{iu}' dP \\ & = - \left\{ N_s \sum_{i=1}^k \left(\frac{\delta \mu_s'}{\delta N'_{ia}} \right)_{T,P,N'_{ia}} \delta N'_{ia} + N_{ia} \sum_{i=1}^k \left(\frac{\delta \mu_{ia}'}{\delta N'_{ia}} \right)_{T,P,N'_{ia}} dN_{ia} \right. \\ & \left. + N_{ic} \sum_{i=1}^k \left(\frac{\delta \mu_{ic}'}{\delta N'_{ia}} \right)_{T,P,N'_{ia}} dN'_{ia} + N_{iu} \sum_{i=1}^k \left(\frac{\delta \mu_{iu}'}{\delta N'_{ia}} \right)_{T,P,N'_{ia}} dN'_{ia} + \dots \text{to } 3k + 1 \text{ terms} \right\} \dots \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

since for each electrolyte, we have to consider the mole fraction of only one of the three species as independent. We have here considered the mole fraction of the anion as independent; but it makes no difference if we consider the mole fraction of the cation or that of the undissociated electrolyte as independent.

We shall also obtain in a similar way

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -\frac{1}{T} \left\{ N', L, + \sum_{i=1}^k N'_{i\alpha} L_{i\alpha} + \sum_{i=1}^k N'_{i\alpha} L_{i\alpha} + \sum_{i=1}^k N'_{i\alpha} L_{i\alpha} \right\} dT \\
 & + \left\{ N', \bar{V}', + \sum_{i=1}^k N'_{i\alpha} \bar{V}'_{i\alpha} + \sum_{i=1}^k N'_{i\alpha} \bar{V}'_{i\alpha} + \sum_{i=1}^k N'_{i\alpha} \bar{V}'_{i\alpha} \right\} dP \\
 & = \left\{ N', \sum_{i=1}^k \left(\frac{\delta \mu_s}{\delta N_{i\alpha}} \right)_{T, P, N_{j\alpha}} dN_{i\alpha} + N'_{i\alpha} \sum_{i=1}^k \left(\frac{\delta \mu_{i\alpha}}{\delta N_{i\alpha}} \right)_{T, P, N_{j\alpha}} dN_{i\alpha} \right. \\
 & \left. + N'_{i\alpha} \sum_{i=1}^k \left(\frac{\delta \mu_{i\alpha}}{\delta N_{i\alpha}} \right)_{T, P, N_{j\alpha}} dN_{i\alpha} + N'_{i\alpha} \sum_{i=1}^k \left(\frac{\delta \mu_{i\alpha}}{\delta N_{i\alpha}} \right)_{T, P, N_{j\alpha}} dN_{i\alpha} + \dots \text{to } 3k+1 \text{ terms} \right\} \dots \quad (7)
 \end{aligned}$$

If we assume all the other species to be non-volatile except the solvent, which is usually the case, equation (7) reduces to the very simple form

$$-\frac{1}{T} N', L', dT + \bar{V}', dP = dN_{i\alpha} \sum_{i=1}^k \left(\frac{\delta \mu_s}{\delta N_{i\alpha}} \right)_{T, P, N_{j\alpha}} dN_{i\alpha} \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

$$\text{or} \quad -\frac{1}{T} \left\{ L,^\circ - (H', - H,^\circ) \right\} dT + \bar{V}', dP = + \sum_{i=1}^k \left(\frac{\delta \mu_s}{\delta N_{i\alpha}} \right)_{T, P, N_{j\alpha}} dN_{i\alpha} \quad (8')$$

For a non-ideal solution, the chemical potential of the solvent is given by the relation

$$\mu_s = \mu_s^\circ + RT \ln a_s \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

where μ_s° depends on temperature and pressure and a_s is the activity of the solvent. Using equation (9) we obtain from equation (8')

$$-\frac{1}{T} \left\{ L,^\circ - (H,^\circ - H,^\circ) \right\} dT + \bar{V}', dP = RT \sum_{i=1}^k \left(\frac{\delta \ln a_s}{\delta N_{i\alpha}} \right)_{T, P, N_{j\alpha}} dN_{i\alpha} \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

This equation can be used to express the variations of boiling point with pressure and composition and of total pressure with composition and so on.

The applicability of this equation, however, is limited because of the approximation already mentioned (that the degree of dissociation does not change with concentration). We shall hence derive formulae assuming complete dissociation of all the electrolytes. This will, in general, be true of strong electrolytes in dilute solutions. Although it is an oversimplification, it is a better model than the one which ignores dissociation into ions. We shall not henceforth distinguish between the different species of electrolytes, but only between the different species of ions. Accordingly, we can describe the compositions of solutions of electrolytes in terms of the molality m_i of each of the ionic species. Since the solution is electrically neutral, we have the following condition of electro-neutrality

$$\sum_i Z_i m_i = 0$$

where the symbol Z_i denotes the charge on an ion i measured in units of the charge of a proton. Owing to this restrictive condition, a solution, containing $\gamma + 1$ species including the ionic species and the solvent has only γ independent components. If, however, the composition is expressed in mole fraction or ion fraction, we shall have only $\gamma - 1$ independent components.

Assuming that all the other species are non-volatile except the solvent, we hence obtain

$$-\frac{1}{T} \left\{ L_1^\circ - (H_1' - H_1^\circ) \right\} dT + \bar{V}_1' dP = \sum_{i=1}^{\gamma-1} \left(\frac{\delta \mu_1}{\delta N_i} \right)_{T,P,N_j} \delta N_i \quad \dots (11)$$

where the subscript 1 represents the solvent.

$$\text{Since} \quad \mu_1 = \mu_1^\circ + RT \ln a_1$$

$$\text{we have} \quad -\frac{1}{T} \left\{ L_1^\circ - (H_1' - H_1^\circ) \right\} dT + \bar{V}_1' dP = RT \Delta \ln a_1 \quad \dots (12)$$

Equation (12) expresses, for constant composition

$$\bar{V}_1' dP = -\frac{1}{T} \left\{ L_1^\circ - (H_1' - H_1^\circ) \right\} dT \quad \dots \quad \dots (13)$$

If the vapour is assumed to be ideal, the above equation can easily show that when $\log P$ is plotted against temperature, a straight line should be obtained, with the help of which the heat of dilution can be computed.

It may be pointed out at this stage that the activity of the solvent can be computed from experimental values of boiling point elevations or freezing point depressions and compared with theoretical expressions. It need not be stressed that the above treatment holds good for solid-liquid equilibrium as well.

Solution of Single Electrolyte in Equilibrium with Non-ideal Vapour

In deriving most of the formulae for solutions of non-electrolytes, it is usually assumed that the solvent behaves as a perfect gas in the vapour phase. Here we shall depart from this tradition and denote explicit formulae, taking into account the non-ideal nature of the vapour phase.

For the case of a solution of a single electrolyte, converting mole fractions into molalities, in equation (12)

$$-\frac{1}{T} (L_1^\circ + \overline{H_1 - H_1^\circ}) dT + \bar{V}_1' dP = \frac{M_1 m_2}{1000} \left(\frac{\delta \mu_1}{\delta m_2} \right)_{T,P} dm_2 \quad \dots (14)$$

where M_1 = molecular weight of the solvent and m_2 = molality of the solution.

$$\text{Now, we have} \quad \mu_1 = \mu_1^\circ + RT \ln a_1 = \mu_1^\circ + RT \ln m_2 \gamma_2,$$

where γ_2 is the activity coefficient referred to the molality scale; hence

$$\left(\frac{\delta \mu_1}{\delta m_2} \right)_{T,P} = \frac{RT}{m_2} + RT \left(\frac{\delta \ln \gamma_2}{\delta m_2} \right)_{T,P} \quad \dots \quad \dots (15)$$

we define $\gamma_{\pm} = \gamma_{+}^{\nu_{+}} \gamma_{-}^{\nu_{-}}$

where ν_{+} and ν_{-} are the numbers of respective ions on dissociation.

The mean activity coefficient $\gamma_{\pm}$ is defined by

$$\gamma_{\pm} = (\gamma_{+}^{\nu_{+}} \gamma_{-}^{\nu_{-}})^{1/\nu}$$

so that $\gamma_{\pm} = \gamma_{\pm}^{\nu}$ and $\ln \gamma_{\pm} = \nu \ln \gamma_{\pm}$ (16)

Making use of (16), we have from equation (14)

$$+ \frac{I}{T} (L_1^{\circ} + \overline{H_1} - H_1^{\circ}) dT + \overline{V_1}' dP = \frac{RTM_1m_2}{1000} \left[\frac{I}{m_2} + \nu \left(\frac{\delta \ln \gamma_{\pm}}{\delta m_2} \right) \right] dm_2 \dots \dots (17)$$

we can substitute for $\ln \gamma_{\pm}$ either from the original Debye-Hückel equation or from the modifications of it proposed by several authors. We mention particularly the equation proposed by Stokes and Robinson, and Glueckauf which take into account the hydration of the ions. These equations have comparatively large ranges of validity (*i. e.* up to about $4m$) and hence can be safely used.

Solid-liquid-vapour Equilibrium

We can easily extend the formalism for studying solid-liquid-vapour equilibrium. In this connection we will consider the variation of vapour pressure of the solvent in a solution containing several electrolytes, kept saturated with the solid phase containing one electrolyte. The treatment will hold good for sparingly soluble electrolytes, so that the solution phase consists of only ions and solvent.

Using subscript 1 for the solvent and 2, 3 etc. for the ionic species, and using superscript (') for the vapour phase, (") for the solid phase and none for the liquid phase, we have for the component (1)

$$- (\overline{S_1}' - \overline{S_1}) dT + (\overline{V_1}' - \overline{V_1}) dP = - \left(\frac{\delta \mu_1}{\delta N_1} \right)_{T,P} . dN_1 \quad \dots \quad \dots (18)$$

Similarity for the other ionic species, we have

$$- (\overline{S_2}'' - \overline{S_2}) dT = - \left(\frac{\delta \mu_2}{\delta N_2} \right)_{T,P} . dN_2 \quad \dots \quad \dots (19)$$

$$- (\overline{S_3}'' - \overline{S_3}) dT = - \left(\frac{\delta \mu_3}{\delta N_3} \right)_{T,P} . dN_3 \quad \dots \quad \dots (20)$$

and so on.

The term containing pressure does not appear in the above equation, since pressure is insignificant for solid-liquid equilibrium.

Multiplying equation (18) and equations (19), (20), by $N_1, N_2, \dots$ and adding and using Gibbs-Duhem relation for the vapour phase, we have

$$- \{ N_1 (\bar{S}_1' - \bar{S}_1) + N_2 (\bar{S}_2'' - \bar{S}_2) + N_3 (\bar{S}_3'' - \bar{S}_3) + \dots \} dT \\ + N_1 (\bar{V}_1' - \bar{V}_1) dP = 0 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (21)$$

Putting $\bar{S}_1' - \bar{S}_1 = \frac{L_1^\circ + (H_1' - H_1^\circ)}{T}$ and $\bar{S}_2'' - \bar{S}_2 = -\frac{L_2}{T}$

where L_1 is the heat of solution and neglecting $\bar{V}_1$, in comparison to $\bar{V}_1'$, we have from equation (21)

$$- \frac{1}{T} \{ N_1 L_1^\circ + N_2 (H_1 - H_1^\circ) - N_2 L_2 \} dT + N_1 \left(\frac{RT}{P} + B + C'P + \dots \right) dP = 0 \quad \dots \quad (22)$$

or
$$\frac{dP}{dT} = \frac{1/T \{ N_1 L_1^\circ + N_1 (H_1 - H_1^\circ) - N_2 L_2 - \dots \}}{N_1 \left\{ \frac{RT}{P} + B + C'P + \dots \right\}} \quad \dots \quad (23)$$

In deducing the above equation we have assumed that only one electrolyte remains in the solid phase. L_2 is the heat of solution of the said electrolyte. It need not be emphasised that the above formula strictly holds for solutions of sparingly soluble electrolytes

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